

Bidding in Local Energy Markets Considering Uncertainty from Renewables and Demand

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Abstract— The penetration of distributed energy resources in distribution networks is currently enabling the emergence of local energy markets (LEM). However, considering renewable generation and load demand variability is crucial to realize such transactive energy systems. In this work, we propose a bi-level optimization model for bidding in LEM, considering the uncertainty of renewables and demand. At the upper-level, consumers, prosumers, and producers submit bids in a double-auction LEM to minimize the cost of consumers and maximize the profits of producers considering PV generation and demand variability. The lower-level corresponds to a pool-based LEM that maximizes the energy transactions of players. The problem complexity calls for alternative solutions methods, such as evolutionary computation, to find near-optimal solutions efficiently. Results suggest that the model can account for the uncertainty that may be realized in the day-ahead for load demand and PV generation but at the expense of a higher overall cost.

Keywords— *Bi-level optimization, Evolutionary computation, Local energy market, Renewable energy, Uncertainty modelling.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Local electricity markets (LEM) are attracting the attention of stakeholders at the distribution level to contribute to the decarbonization and decentralization of the energy systems. These new market structures are accompanied by investments in renewable distributed generation and push for the participation of end-users as active players of the market [1]. The participation (or competition) between players in the local market is typically categorized in consensus-based, bilateral trades, and double-auction models. Under these models, end-users are empowered to take part in the energy community and promote the transition to a sustainable energy system [2].

However, the interactions of market players in LEM (and in systems involving renewable generation, variable demand, and volatile market prices) face issues related to resource variability, pushing towards the analysis of competition of market participants from different perspectives in the literature (e.g., agent-based systems, game-theoretic approaches, machine learning, etc.) [3]–[5]. Furthermore, congestion issues can also arise in this new paradigm [6] and LEM can provide an efficient framework to involve small participants to quickly cooperate [7]. Uncertainty, for instance in renewable generation, demand, and market prices, impact the expected profits of participants and can put at risk the planning and operation of the grid, leaving the burden of balancing and correction of such deviations to trading close to real-time and upper levels of the energy chain [8], [9].

In this work, we take a step forward in modeling LEM by considering the uncertainty of renewables and the variability of demand. Our approach is based in [10], and consider a LEM

with consumers, prosumers, and small combined heat and power (CHP) generators participating in a day-ahead double-auction LEM. It is assumed that players are equipped with different equipment such as smart meters or home management systems that allow some degree of automation and control to exchange energy with peers. Also, an aggregator/retailer is considered to guarantee that energy consumption is satisfied (despite the variability of demand) and that excess of PV generation is injected into the grid for a feed-in tariff.

The problem is formulated as a bi-level optimization model, extending the model from [10] by incorporating the uncertainty of load demand and PV generation. The work in [10] does not consider the uncertainty of renewables and load demand, which can impact the operation phase after the trading window is closed. This work covers such issue by modelling uncertainty using a scenario-based approach. The upper-level considers the costs minimization of consumers and the profits maximization of producers bidding in the LEM, while the lower-level maximize the transacted energy representing a pool-based market that collects all price/quantity bids from participants and clears the market. An evolutionary algorithm (EA), the vortex search (VS) algorithm, is used to optimize the bids/offers of market players under variable demand and PV generation.

The main contributions of the paper are: i) an extension of the model for optimization of energy bids in LEM proposed in [10], incorporating the consideration of the uncertainty of demand and PV generation; ii) Uncertainty modeling considering a scenarios generation and reduction technique; iii) an EA framework to solve the problem using evolutionary computation; iv) analysis of a case study considering players of different types participating in the LEM.

II. LEM BIDDING OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM UNDER UNCERTAINTY

In this article, a LEM bidding optimization problem, for the day-ahead, is considered with players submitting bids/offers to maximize their profits (or equivalently minimize their costs). We assume three types of agents, consumers, prosumers (i.e., consumers with PV generation capabilities, and small producers (i.e., CHP units). The players have backup energy provided by an aggregator/utility if the LEM is insufficient to satisfy the demand. As in [10], [11], players put bids of price in the LEM between a feed-in tariff (c^F) and the aggregator tariff (c^{agg}). It is assumed that $c^F < c^{agg}$ to guarantee that the LEM favors local transactions rather than buying/selling energy from the grid. Since players are participating in the day-ahead, uncertainty of demand and PV generation should be taken into account to minimize the possible effect of deviation in the operation phase. To this end, this work incorporates uncertainty of demand and PV

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generation by considering several diverse possible scenarios over variables associated with these devices. Figure 1 illustrates the LEM concept used in this work.

Fig. 1. Considered LEM structure. The LEM responds to the bids and offers sending the clearing price cp_t and transacted energy $X_{i,j}$ to the market participants. The aggregator/retailer acts as a backup to guarantee supply of demand and avoid PV deviations due to uncertainty.

A bi-level optimization model, similar to [10], is proposed. The model considers the minimization/maximization of costs/incomes at the upper-level (multi-leader problem) and maximizes energy transactions at the lower-level (single-follower problem). The main difference with [10] is considering the uncertainty of demand and PV generation into the model. To this end, different scenarios are considered, along with their probability of occurrence.

A. Uncertainty representation

A technique for scenario generation and reduction used in [2] is applied to find a set of scenarios that represent probabilistic characteristics of load profiles and PV generation of players adequately. In this method, different scenarios (a large number is recommended) are generated with Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS). The method considers the probability distribution function of the forecasted errors (obtained, e.g., by using historical data): $X_{(t)}^s = X_{(t)}^{\text{forecast}} + X_{(t)}^{\text{error},s}$, where $X_{(t)}^{\text{error},s}$ is a zero-mean noise with standard deviation σ . To simplify the modeling, although accuracy is lost, the forecast errors related to the uncertainty are represented by a normal distribution function.

A scenario reduction technique is used to exclude scenarios with a low probability of occurrence and combine scenarios that are statistically close to each other without losing the high accuracy of the model (see [2], [12] for further details). In this way, the size of the problem is reduced without losing the statistical properties of the initial set of scenarios, and the computational burden is avoided.

B. Mathematical model

Thus, let us consider a set of consumers $I = \{1, 2, \dots, N_c\}$ and producers $J = \{1, 2, \dots, N_p\}$ where each i th consumer player searches for the minimization of costs and each j th producer (either a prosumer or small generator) searches for the maximization of profits. The bids from consumers are modelled as a tuple $(b_{i,t}, g_{i,t})$, where $b_{i,t}$ is the price proposed by the player to buy the amount of energy $d_{i,t}$ at time t . On the other hand, offers from producers are modelled as $(b_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$, where $b_{j,t}$ is a price offer to sell the amount of energy $g_{j,t}$ at

time t . The minimization of costs for each consumer, considering uncertainty in their generation, is formulated as:

$$C_i = \sum_{s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_j cp_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^{\text{agg}} \cdot E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}} \right) \cdot \pi(s) \quad (1a)$$

st.

$$d_{i,t,s}^{\text{Total}} = \sum_{j,j \neq i} x_{j,i,t} + E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq c_t^F \leq cp_t \leq b_{i,t} \leq c_t^{\text{agg}} \quad (1c)$$

$$x_{j,i,t}, E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}}, b_{i,t}, d_{i,t} \geq 0, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (1d)$$

where cp_t is the clearing price resulting from the activities in the local market; $x_{j,i,t}$ is the transacted energy between player j and i ; c_t^{agg} is a tariff that the aggregator manage with the agents; and $E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}}$ is the energy acquired from the aggregator/utility by agent i to supply its demand. $\pi(s)$ is the probability that scenario s occurs. Constraints (1b) guarantees that the uncertain demand $d_{i,t,s}^{\text{Total}}$ is fulfilled across all scenarios, constraint (1c) guarantees that the LEM clearing price is lower or equal to the bidding price of agent i , and Eq. (1d) represents variable definition bounds.

On the other hand, producer players (either prosumers with PV generation or small generators) look for the maximization of profits considering uncertainty as:

$$P_j = \sum_{s=1}^{N_s} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\sum_i cp_t \cdot x_{j,i,t} + c_t^F \cdot E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}} - c_t^m \cdot G_{j,t} \right) \cdot \pi(s) \quad (2a)$$

st.

$$g_{j,t,s}^{\text{Total}} = \sum_{i,j \neq i} x_{j,i,t} + E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}} \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2b)$$

$$0 \leq c_t^F \leq b_{i,t} \leq cp_t \leq c_t^{\text{agg}} \quad (2c)$$

$$x_{j,i,t}, E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}}, b_{j,t}, g_{j,t} \geq 0, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2d)$$

where again cp_t is the LEM clearing price (same for consumer and producers), $x_{j,i,t}$ is the transaction of energy between producer j and consumer i ; the feed-in tariff or cost is c_t^F ; $E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}}$ is the remaining energy that producer/prosumer j injects to the grid (considering different scenarios of PV production), and $c_t^m \cdot G_{j,t}$ is the marginal cost of either the PV generation or a small CHP generator j . It is assumed that $c_t^m = 0$ for the solar PV generation, and $c_t^m = C^{\text{CHP}}(G_{j,t})$, the marginal cost of the CHP, is defined as [13]:

$$C^{\text{CHP}}(G_{j,t}) = \frac{b_{\text{CHP}} \cdot \sqrt{G_{j,t}}}{G_{j,t}} \quad (3)$$

where b_{CHP} is a cost factor of the CHP unit and $G_{j,t}$ is the energy produced by the small CHP.

The new formulation considers now the variability of demand $d_{i,t,s}^{\text{Total}}$ and PV generation $g_{j,t,s}^{\text{Total}}$ from prosumers. However, this distribution only affects the upper-level calculation, since the bidding in the LEM depends only on the bids/offers $(b_{i,t}, d_{i,t})/(b_{j,t}, g_{j,t})$ which are independent on the scenario. Notice, however, that the response of the market

(cp_t) affects the calculation of costs/profits along the set of scenarios. In the lower-level, we model a symmetric pool market using a merit order procedure based on the price of bids/offers. This type of allocation determines the clearing or equilibrium price (i.e., the cp_t) by forming supply and demand curves and obtaining the point at which supply equals demand. The formulation follows:

$$\text{maximize } X^{\text{LEM}} = GE_v \cup DE_w \quad (4a)$$

st.

$$cp_t = \max(b_j(GE_v)) \quad (4b)$$

$$cp_t, X^{\text{LEM}} \geq 0 \quad (4c)$$

where X^{LEM} is the amount of energy transacted in the LEM; GE is the set of offers of energy $g_{j,t}$ in ascending price order; DE is the set of bids for energy $d_{i,t}$ in descending price order; GE_v and DE_w are used to describe when supply and demand curves intersect, i.e., when the aggregated offers and bids attain the condition $b_v \leq b_w$. Thus, the clearing price at each time t (cp_t) is determined by the highest offer still accepted in the LEM merit order procedure.

III. EVOLUTIONARY COMPUTATION TO SOLVE THE LEM OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM UNDER UNCERTAINTY

Due to the complexity of the problem (a bi-level optimization with multiple equilibrium points) that now incorporates uncertainty in variables, alternative solution methods are justified providing a more flexible approach to deal with such a model. Therefore, we advocate the use of evolutionary computation (EC) algorithms. EC encompasses global optimization algorithms mostly inspired by evolutionary processes [15]. From the wide variety of these approaches, evolutionary algorithms (EA) have effectively tackled problems with diverse characteristics in different domains. Typically, EAs are population-based solvers that improve a set of solutions over a given number of iterations, evolving them until a stop criterion is met. The performance of solutions is measured by a fitness function tightly related to the objective function of the problem faced. Solutions are generated at each iteration using different mechanisms and operators, replacing solutions that show low performance in the fitness function. Empirical studies have shown that under these EAs, the solutions evolve gradually towards a promising area of the search space (similarly to what the principles of natural/artificial selection dictate) [15].

Without loss of generality over many different EAs, these methods require a solution representation (i.e., encoding of solutions) and a fitness function to measure their performance. The following subsections describe these two components and the approaches to be used in this work.

A. Encoding of solutions and fitness function

Players search for the minimization/maximization of costs/profits according to their bidding decisions in the LEM. In this work, the uncertainty from renewables and demand has to be taken into account. Thus, assuming a set of players $K = \{1, 2, \dots, N_k\}$ (Notice that, different from Section II, in which producers and consumers are separated in two groups, this K), searching for the best tuple $(q_{k,t}, p_{k,t}) \forall k \in K, t \in T$, representing optimal bids of energy $q_{k,t}$ and price $p_{k,t}$ at each time $t \in T$, we define a vector $\vec{x} = \{[q_{k,t} \cup p_{k,t}]\}$ that contains all the bids/offers from players into the LEM. A sign convention is used to identify consumer or producer player

types. A positive value represents a buying into the LEM (bid), and a negative value represents selling into the LEM (offer). In the original formulation [10], the player actions are bounded by the variable allowed limits. For instance, consumers send bids into the LEM between $[0, d_{i,t,s}^{\text{Total}}]$ (i.e., considering the range of 0 consumption and maximum expected consumption), while generators or prosumers between $[-g_{j,t,s}^{\text{Total}}, 0]$ (i.e., in the range of 0 production and maximum production capacity). However, these bound limits are now influenced by the scenario under consideration (i.e., $d_{i,t,s}^{\text{Total}}$ and $g_{j,t,s}^{\text{Total}}$ depend on the scenario s). To avoid this problem, we encoded the bids of consumers and prosumers between $[0, 1]$ representing a percentage of the quantity of energy they want to bid/offer in the market. The bounds for prices are the same for all agents and within the range $[c_t^F, c_t^{\text{agg}}] \forall t \in T$.

The performance of the encoded solution \vec{x} must be evaluated in the fitness function (which is related to the objective function Eqs. (1a-2a)). Therefore, using the information of \vec{x} we compute the individual distributed costs/profits as:

$$U_{k,t} = \begin{cases} -C_{i,t} & \text{if } k \text{ is a consumer agent} \\ P_{j,t} & \text{if } k \text{ is a generator agent} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $C_{i,t}$ and $P_{j,t}$ are objectives in conflict since agents want to achieve the best result for themselves. In this work, we adopt the perspective from [10] to approximate the optimal solution of a cooperative model by calculating the average profits summing over all agents and considering such sum Pareto optimal [16]. Therefore, the fitness function is modeled as:

$$\text{Fit}(\vec{x}) = -\text{mean}(A_{\text{profit}}) + \text{std}(A_{\text{profit}}) \quad (6)$$

where $A_{\text{profit}} = [U_1, \dots, U_k, \dots, U_{N_k}]$ is an array including all the costs/profits achieved by the agents; **mean()** and **std()** are functions that compute the average and standard deviation of the costs/profits of all agents. The negative sign in the first term is used to transform profits maximization into a minimization problem.

Figure 2 shows the mechanism to evaluate a solution in the fitness function. First, for each solution, a decoding process from the vector solution \vec{x} is done to retrieve the bids/offers from players. At each period t , we calculate the clearing price (cp_t) and the energy transacted in the LEM using the merit order mechanism described in Eq. (4a). The costs/profits of each player can be calculated using Eqs. (1a-2a). Notice that this calculation now has to be done over all the possible scenarios to get the weighted objective value considering the probability of occurrence. In addition, a deterministic process is implemented to determine the energy traded through the aggregator in all scenarios, i.e., variables $E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}}$ and $E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}}$ in Eqs. (1a-2a). $E_{i,t,s}^{\text{buy}} = d_{i,t,s}^{\text{total}} - \sum_j x_{j,i,t}$ models the remaining energy not obtained in the LEM to satisfy the consumer demand over the set of possible scenarios. For producers, on the other hand, we have two situations handled in different ways. The first situation is when producer k is a CHP generator; in that case, a restriction is imposed to avoid generators selling energy to the grid at the feed-in tariff (since that situation is not realistic). The second situation occurs when producer k is a prosumer with excess of PV generation; in that case, the prosumer is forced to inject the excess of ener-

Fig. 2. Considered LEM structure. The LEM responds to the bids and offers sending the clearing price cp_t and transacted energy $x_{j,i,t}$ to market participants. The aggregator/retailer acts as a backup to guarantee supply of demand and avoid PV deviations due to uncertainty.

gy that was not traded in the LEM into the grid at the feed-in tariff (i.e., the $E_{j,t,s}^{\text{sell}} = g_{j,t,s}^{\text{total}} - \sum_{i,i \neq j} x_{j,i,t}$). Additionally, a direct repair mechanism is implemented in the algorithms to avoid CHP producers bidding a price $b_{j,t}$ lower than the marginal cost of their generation bid $g_{j,t}$. Finally, a penalty is added to the resulting fitness value each time the market is not cleared. This penalty is necessary to direct the search towards feasible solutions that clear the LEM.

B. Evolutionary Algorithms

Under this general structure, we can apply algorithms such as differential evolution (DE), vortex search (VS), or hybrid approaches as HyDE and HyDE-DF [17]. Since the scope of this article is not focused on the development of EAs, the reader can be referred to [10] for details on the implementation of different approaches. Here, we briefly explain the most noticeable characteristics of the selected approaches for optimization in this work, the VS algorithm.

VS is a single-solution-based metaheuristic with a framework similar to other EAs [18]. The algorithm generates N_{neighbor} new solutions in the neighborhood (similar to a population of solutions in EAs) using a multivariate Gaussian distribution around the single-solution. At each iteration, the N_{neighbor} solutions are evaluated in the fitness functions, and the single-solution is replaced/updated by the solution with the best fitness. The process is iteratively repeated until a stop criterion is achieved. Thus, VS achieves a balance of exploration and exploitation, decreasing the radius of the neighborhood of the single-solution in the iterative process (emulating a vortex phenomenon). The reader can consult [18] for a detailed explanation of the VS algorithm, and [19] for an example of the application of VS to the optimal bidding problem.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, a case study with different types of players is introduced to apply VS later to solve the problem and analyze the results.

A. Case Studies

We adopt the case study of a previous model without uncertainty published in [10], namely with nine players, three consumers, three prosumers (i.e., consumers with PV generation), and three small CHP generators. The original case study is based on sampling power profiles of residential

houses and PV systems based on open datasets available on PES ISS website (Open data online at <http://sites.ieee.org/pes-iss/data-sets/>). We apply the scenario uncertainty representation to this case study according to the methodology depicted in Sect. II-A. We also consider generator agents corresponding to CHPs with a maximum generation capacity of 2kW and a marginal cost calculated with Eq. (3) with a factor $b_{\text{CHP}} = 0.10$ EUR/kWh [13]. Finally, feed-in tariff is set to $c_t^F = 0.095$ EUR/kWh and the aggregator tariff varies in function of the WS market plus an aggregator fee of 0.15 EUR/kWh resulting in an average tariff of $c_t^{\text{agg}} = 0.1983$ EUR/kWh as in [10].

Fig. 3. Profiles used in the case study. An error of 10% around the mean value for PV generation and 15% around the demand was used to create the scenarios. Ranges of power (in kW): house 1 [0.18-0.48], house 2 [0.06-2.50], house 3 [0.07-0.36], PV (house) [0-1].

Regarding the selected EA and the settings of experiments, VS evaluates in each iteration N_{neighbor} solutions, which results in several function evaluations equal to the product of neighbor solutions and the number of iterations (i.e., $FE = N_{\text{neighbor}} \cdot N_{\text{iter}}$). However, the consideration of uncertainty makes the fitness function more expensive than normal since the total number of considered scenarios should be evaluated for each solution. While this increases the accuracy of the solutions obtained (making them more robust to the variability of outcomes), the number of function evaluations increases according to $FE = N_{\text{neighbor}} \cdot N_{\text{iter}} \cdot N_s$. The experiments were implemented in MATLAB 2018a in a computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8650U CPU@1.90GHz processor with 16GB of RAM running Windows 10. The number of neighbor solutions was set to $N_{\text{neighbor}} = 5$, with 1000 iterations despi-

TABLE I. OVERALL COSTS/PROFITS, FITNESS, AND TIME ACHIEVED IN EACH CASE STUDY.

Case study	Overall Cost (EUR)	Cost/profits by group of players (EUR)			Fitness	Std	Penalty	Time (mins)
		Costs (EUR)		Profits (EUR)				
		Consumers	Prosumers	Producers				
No uncertainty	1.95	2.50	0.43	-0.98	1.69	0.08	0.00	2.47
10 Scenarios	2.10	2.77	0.68	-1.35	1.89	0.08	0.00	24.31
100 Scenarios	2.10	2.77	0.69	-1.36	1.92	0.08	0.03	242.43

te the number of scenarios considered. 20 trials have been performed for each case study, and the average values (and the best solutions) have been reported. For this study, we have considered consumers and prosumers with no elasticity of price and demand bidding the maximum amount of consumption/ generation at the maximum price, if the LEM provides cheaper energy than the retailer. In such conditions, producers become the price-setters due to the merit order mechanism and need to optimize their offers in function also of the possible scenarios.

B. Results and Discussion

The overall results simulated in this paper can be observed in Table \ref{tab1:Results}. More precisely, this table depicts the overall costs of the system, costs (consumer and prosumer players) and profits (small CHP producer players), the fitness function value obtained by the adopted EA, and the execution time achieved by in the different case studies. The scenario without uncertainty provides an overall cost of 1.95 EUR, while this cost inevitably increases when uncertainty is considered, i.e., 2.10 EUR. In fact, the expected profits of the producers are higher (up to 39%). Conversely, the expected costs of the consumers increase up to 60%. The difference between solutions with scenarios is negligible when comparing this solution without considering scenarios (8%).

It can be seen that the optimization method can navigate the search landscape and retrieve solutions without penalties, i.e., after the imposed number of iterations has been reached. The total time shown in minutes, i.e., 2.47 minutes without uncertainty, 24 minutes with 10 scenarios and 242 with 100 scenarios, provides a picture of the linear nature of the time complexity involved by the EA.

Fig. 4 shows the overall energy traded by individual players, namely, without uncertainty (no scenarios), 10 scenarios, and 100 scenarios. We present in blue bars the energy traded in the LEM, and in orange bars the energy sell/bought to/from the grid through the aggregator/retailer. The individual player results show the same trend in each case. This is expected since the consumers/prosumers have no elasticity, which, according to our earlier assumption, bid all the possible amount they can relying upon that LEM is advantageous. In fact, considering the elasticity of price of consumers would affect the results since more competition would take place in the LEM. However, the short-term price elasticity of the consumers is generally accepted as very low and can be neglected in this study [20]. The energy trading with the retailer mostly corresponds to the surplus energy from PV that cannot be fully fulfilled in LEM and needs to be injected into the grid at the feed-in tariff. Nevertheless, differences can still be noticed since the adopted method is stochastic. While results show a certainty trend, further experiments need to be done to analyze the impact of

uncertainty in the day-ahead and assess the computational burden when more agents are considered. Also, the robustness of the optimization approach (in this case, VS) should be contrasted with other methods in future work to guarantee good performance under different circumstances and several scenarios.

Fig. 4. Overall profits achieved by individual agents: (a) No uncertainty; (b) 10 scenarios; (c) 100 scenarios.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a step forward in researching the optimal bidding problem in local energy markets, namely, considering renewables and energy loads. We introduce modeling of uncertainty in PV generation and load demand in the bi-level problem. To the best of our knowledge, this attempt has not been made before for this specific bidding model. The problem is modeled as a stochastic optimization approach using a scenario reduction technique approach. Moreover, we adopt vortex search as the preferred EA algorithm following the good results we obtained in earlier research. While we cannot guarantee an optimal solution to the problem, the empirical experiments performed indicate that solutions are competitive and can be applied in practice, reducing costs for consumers, increasing profits for producers, and achieving an efficient local market with competitive prices. We realize by the experiments in this paper that considering uncertainty in the bidding model may ultimately increase the LEM clearing price, i.e., increase expected costs for consumers and expected profits of producers. This would protect the agents against a set of scenarios that may realize ahead. To counteract the impact of underlying uncertainty, a set of possibilities could be studied in future works, including the effect of energy storage systems and the elasticity of demand. In addition, we will investigate the possibility of including risk strategies, i.e., Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR), in a future version of this work, namely using risk-averse and risk-neutral strategies objective functions for comparison [8], [9].

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